
Teaching English Poetry in EFL Classroom through Classroom Presentation

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Abstract

The objective of this research was to know about how to teach English poetry in the EFL classroom through classroom presentation. Poetry has been used in teaching and learning English in the classroom. Many educators have attempted to deal with poetry in the EFL classroom. English poetry is a subject in the fifth semester of the English Department at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate. The research design used in this research is qualitative research. The population in this research was all students of the English Department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate, and the samples of this research were 20 fifth-semester students of the English department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate. To collect the data the researcher used classroom observation and documentation. To analyze the data, the researcher was analyzed the data from the result of classroom observation or in other words the researcher analyzes the result of classroom presentation. The analysis showed that classroom presentation can enhance the students' achievement in learning poetry.

Keywords: *poetry, classroom presentation, teaching poetry, improvement*

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1. Background

Literature has been widely used in teaching and learning English nowadays. Some theoretical discussions and some case studies have supported the relevance of using literature in foreign language teaching. Literature is considered a promising tool for language learning purposes. Literary exploration can be used to enhance the efficiency of language learning programs and also gives some advantages in the classroom (Van, 2009). Literature also fosters learners' motivation to read and write which also can improve their reading and writing proficiency to serve their academic and occupational needs (McKay, in Bagherkazemi & Alemi, 2010).

Among the literary genres used in language teaching is poetry, poetry is one of frequent appearance. Poems become favorite tools for language teachers due to their short length, perfectly suitable for a single classroom lesson, their peculiar structure, and their linguistic

characteristic features. The evocative character of poetry, its imagery, its appeal to feelings, and personal experience make it very interesting and enjoyable for the second/foreign language learners (Llach, 2007). The fact that poetry deviates from normal language that has some unusual ways of ordering words, imaginative meanings to words, or combines sounds in a musical, non-ordinary way and style deviation makes poetry important and useful in the language classroom. The language teacher should exploit the deviancies of the poetic language to arise the language awareness of the learners towards how language can be adapted or changed to fulfill different communicative purposes.

Poetry has been used in teaching and learning English in the classroom. Many educators have attempted to deal with poetry in the EFL classroom. The Northern Territory Department of Employment, Education and Training in Australia (2006) proposed resources in teaching and learning poetry. They state that poetry is a language used in particular ways that involve rhyme, rhythm, and meter. It is a way of sharing experiences, telling a story, expressing feelings or ideas. Poetry appeals to the imagination throughout the form, rhythm, and word choice that can create vivid visual images for the audience. Poems can paint powerful, sharp pictures using images and emotive language which stimulates senses.

Poetry as a way to develop students' literacy competence has some benefits in EFL classrooms. According to Panavelli (2011), the benefits of poetry in EFL classroom are: (1) It can be used as a valuable resource to introduce and practice the language by exposing students to authentic models –real language in a context which can develop their language skills, (2) it provides students with an opportunity to enrich their vocabulary in a new way by offering meaningful context which can be used and remembered effectively, (3) It encourages students in developing their creativity where they can discover interesting ideas for creative writing simultaneously, (4) It is motivating as it generates strong emotional reactions, (5) it provides students with insight into developing cross-cultural awareness which helps them in acquiring fluency in the target language, (6) it deals with universal themes and human concerns which offers opportunities to project students feelings and emotions, thus fostering personal involvement in learners.

Bringing up poetry in the EFL classroom sometimes is hard for the teachers. One of the challenges is the choice of poetry that suits each student. The types of poetry that can be used are plenty. However, a teacher should be extremely careful while choosing the text that she/he wants to deal with in the classroom. Poetry that will be taught to students should have an appropriate level of complexity that challenges but not intimidate. It includes themes and contents that resonate with students which encourages discussion between class members, provokes emotional responses from the students, and does not require too much teacher-centered model (Rush, 2001). Moreover, the needs of the students, their motivation, interest, and cultural background should be taken into consideration while selecting a poem for classroom teaching (Panavelli, 2011). The poem selected should be appropriate in length and of the level of students' comprehension. The selection of the poems is the most important thing in teaching poetry because it influences the students' reactions, perceptions, and motivation in learning poetry especially for the EFL learners.

Talking about English poetry, the researcher will describe how to teach English poetry to the students in the EFL classroom through classroom presentation. Because English poetry is a subject in the fifth semester of the English Department at STKIP KIE RAHA TERNATE. Before students take the subject of English poetry, they have taken and passed the subjects of introduction to literature in the

third semester and prose in the fourth semester. In the English poetry subject, the students learn about basic versification of English poem like stanzaic forms in a poem, rhythms, rhyme scheme, metrical lines, poetic feet, punctuation, and figurative language in a poem. In these cases, the students were asked to look after an English poem and then make an analysis of basic versification of English poem after that they were present in front of the class. The objective of this research was to know how to teach English poetry in the EFL classroom.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Poetry

Poetry as defined by English Dictionary is a genre of literature in which the words and expressions are the focal point and intervene together in an aesthetic, vigorous, and unique way to convey feelings and thoughts. Poetry is a literary work that gives a deep understanding of poets' feelings and other cultures rhythmically.

Mittal (2014) defines poetry as "a piece of writing in which words are arranged beautifully and rhythmically" (p. 21). "Poetry is embellished with rhythm, beautiful diction, and elevated grammatical features" (Ahmad, 2014, p. 123). Wordsworth defined poetry as "the spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings" (1989, p. 57).

Poetry is a way of sharing experiences, telling a story, expressing feelings or ideas. Poetry appeals to the imagination through the form, rhythm, and word choice that can create vivid visual images for the audience. (Antika, 2016, p.27).

2.2. The Characteristics of English Poetry

Poetry stands out from the other literary genres, as it is more impressive and effective in the way that reaches the readers. Poetry is a valuable authentic material, which motivates students to learn the language in an energetic, enjoyable, and motivating way. Antika (2016) believes that poetry emerges from other literary works, which makes it valuable and vital in the classroom. Poetry has its style in presenting and joining words to offer various, touching, and fictional meanings. Also, poetry joins sound in a musical or rhythmic style, which makes it stand out from other genres.

Mittal (2014) deems that what makes poetry so special is its language. For example, poetry uses metaphorical language to convey the intended meaning. Poetry employs varied ways to transfer the writers' ideas and feelings such as using similes, images, synonyms, expressions, symbols, and metaphors.

Kong (2010) highlights the features of poetry as the following: musical sound effects, concise expressions, and rich images. Poetry has a musical sound effect since poetry is full of strong, regular, repeated patterns and movement with stressed and unstressed syllables along with rhyme, which grants poems beautiful harmony. Furthermore, poetry is featured with concise expressions. Poets utilize words in various and distinct methods to transmit their ideas, emotions, and moral lessons and to evoke learners' imagination and interest to learn the language. Moreover, poetry is full of images in which poets use to convey their emotions, intentions, and thoughts, reading poetry can arouse students' interest in the language as they touch the beauty of the language that poets use.

Rasinski and Padak contend "the rhythmical nature of [some] poems and rhymes makes them easy to learn to read and fun to read again and again, which is the main method for developing basic reading fluency in children" (as cited in Roebuck, 2015, p.3).

The researcher believes that poetry is more suitable than other literary genres, due to the following characteristics: First, poetry sometimes is short in terms of length in contrast to short stories, novels, and plays, which will help both teachers and students to handle at a limited time since it usually explores one theme. Besides, poetry is memorable and enjoyable as it is a source of amusement; as well, poetry tackles different themes such as love, hatred, human nature, friendship, tranquility, politics, and economy that students are familiar with or even are interested in. Therefore, poetry is more applicable to all levels ranging from beginners to advanced and for all ages from young learners to adults and all classes.

2.3. The Importance of Poetry in the Classroom

Benton and Fox opine "the main objective of using poetry in language lessons is to find a means of involving the learners in using their language skills actively and creatively and thus to contribute to the development of their communicative competence" (as cited in Ahmad, 2014, p. 124).

Panavelli (2011) underlines the significance of using poetry in EFL classes according to what many ESL/EFL practitioners contend:

1. Poetry is an authentic material, offering students a real context can be a beneficial source to develop and reinforce learners' knowledge of language skills.
2. Poetry gives learners the chance to improve and widen their repertoire of vocabulary in a more genuine way in which learners can retain and recall easily.
3. Poetry enhances learners' creativity. Poetry elicits students' attention to the beautiful and challenging ideas which students can exploit for creative writing.
4. Poetry based activities stimulate learners' emotional reactions. As Hess (2003) realizes that bringing a literary text in the classroom with careful and convenient instructions on behalf of the teacher leads to a perfect and successful collaboration among learners which other genres cannot generate.
5. Poetry offers learners the opportunity to gain an accurate and deep understanding of other cultures, which can facilitate their fluency in the target language (Lazar, 1996).
6. Poetry deals with themes common to all human issues where learners can consolidate their sensation and passion, so learners can boost their involvement (Heath, 1996).

Rachmatia (2015) indicates the advantages of using poetry in the classroom as follows. First, using poetry in the classroom helps teachers to elicit students' creativity. Second, integrating poetry in the teaching process enlivens and gives vitality and enthusiasm to the classroom atmosphere as it influences students' interaction. Also, through poetry teachers can teach the language areas such as grammar, etc. Moreover, through poetry students can construct a positive attitude towards the language and its culture.

Poetry is a fruitful source of reading and a vital example of creative language since it deals with various items in context as well it draws students' attention to intonation, stress, rhyme, rhythm, and pronunciation (Kellem, 2009).

According to Tomlinson, integrating poetry has six advantages as follows: First, educational value. Poetry can evolve students' awareness of other cultures as well as enhances learners' skills of the language along with their personalities as they become more confident to share their thoughts with others. Second, affective value. Poetry tackles various and universal themes that are close and catchy to learners' lives which stimulates and catches learners' attention to take part in the learning process. Third, achievement value. Poetry can enlarge learners' performance when teachers provide varied pre-reading activities to enhance interaction and communication among learners, which will promote learner's role in the class. Fourth, individual value. Integrating poetry in the classroom assists learners to unbridle their imaginations to interpret the content or concept of poems. Fifth, stimulus value. Poetry can evoke learners' creativity and innovation, which correspondingly can direct the students to use the language more conveniently. Sixth, skills development. Poetry can be a profitable source to arouse learners' reading skills like guessing and inferring the meaning of the words from context or linking the content to experience (as cited in Rachmatia, 2015).

Mittal (2014) suggests that poetry has an integral role in the teaching and learning process for several causes. First of all, using poetry in the language classroom enhances interaction and communication among peers or groups of students, since poetry is fictional and has different and potential explanations; this encourages learners to interact without the fear of making mistakes as well as fosters their fluency and accuracy. Second, since poetry has unique features like rhyme, rhythm, and pitch, reading poetry aloud fosters students' self-esteem as well as helps them to express their feelings freely. On the other hand, integrating poetry promotes students' fluency, so using poetry from kindergarten is a good way to learn a language. Also, using poetry in the language classroom supports the four skills of the language (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) which raises motivation among learners. Furthermore, since poetry is not restricted to grammatical matters, teachers only need to use appropriate ways to explain vocabulary; thus, students can learn the target language harmoniously.

Kong (2010) believes that English poetry can be a beneficial source in extensive reading and teaching for the following reasons: enhancing learners' motivation, stimulating learners' imagination, broadening learners' experience, and improving learners' self-cultivation. Enhancing learners' motivation, Kong affirms that reading English poetry stimulates students' attention and interest in learning the language as poetry has a musical melody which encourages students to enjoy its aesthetic feature. Also, she explains that poetry is full of pithy expressions and meaningful images, which evoke students' interest to investigate the power of language and arouse their appreciation towards the language. Moreover, reading English poetry reactivity as it stirs their senses and comprehension, and it enriches students' imagination with its aesthetic forms. Furthermore, she indicates that reading poetry broadens learners' experience: reading poetry gives the readers a better understanding of life and expands their experiences, as poets deal with different human themes to help learners gain a deep awareness of life. Finally, she marks that poetry with its aesthetic features improves learners' self-cultivation. Reading poetry will help learners to become more cultivated as poetry gives learners the chance to edify their personalities as they are influenced by the poets' feeling.

Kırkgöz (2008) explains that poetry is a valuable source to introduce and use a language. Besides, he deems that poetry gives learners the chance to enrich their knowledge about different themes such as death, love, etc.

Stange and Wyant (2008) argue that using poetry at primary grades helps learners to develop self-confidence and self-discipline as they tackle various human issues; it also promotes students' roles in the class as it encourages students to discuss their opinions and feelings. Besides, combining poetry in the classroom evolves learners' literacy as well as their understanding of vocabulary. Furthermore, poetry enhances learners' knowledge about other cultures.

"Poetry can pave the way for the learning and teaching of basic language skills" (Hişmanoğlu, 2005, p. 60). Through poetry, students increase their language proficiency and enhance their motivation especially for those learners who find learning from a textbook is something tedious. Further, learning through poetry may allow students to connect what they learn and how they learn it as poetry deals with different human themes like hatred, human nature, friendship, tranquility, politics, and economy. Moreover, teaching language through poetry creates a catchy environment for better learning because not only it provides a genuine and authentic context for communication, but because it gives pleasure by involving emotions.

Guizar (1992) indicates that using poetry in the classroom gives students' the chance to improve their language skills and enhance their knowledge about other cultures. In addition, she adds that merging poetry in the classroom changes students' ideas about the language itself from being just a language to learn into a language that students can use to express their thoughts, feelings in a beautiful way and be imaginative and thoughtful learners.

Ahmad (2014) examines the effects of using a stylistic or communicative approach to teaching poetry as a tool to evolve grammar, vocabulary, and integrated language skills of Saudi ESL learners. The researcher employs four statistical surveys to draw out his data from both teachers and learners. The sample of this study is two hundred, one hundred teachers, and one hundred students from different Saudi colleges and universities. The results of this research suggest that students who learn poetry through a communicative approach can achieve and enhance both language and linguistics skills better than other students who traditionally learn poetry. Also, the researcher points out that learners show a high degree of motivation and creativity. The researcher concludes that there is a remarkable difference in the performance between traditional learners and Stylistics-based learners in learning the accent, grammar, vocabulary, and integrated language skills.

Reilly (2012) pinpoints that poetry has a crucial role in developing students' pronunciation and vocabulary. Also, she points out that reading poetry helps learners to expand their knowledge about other language aspects such as semantics, syntax, and pragmatics. Moreover, it assists learners to enhance cultural awareness, self-expression, and motivation.

Poetry can serve as a good tool for teaching and learning vocabulary because learning vocabulary in context helps students to understand the meanings of sentences and their semantic and linguistics functions. Otherwise, teaching vocabulary in isolation as lists that should be memorized leads students to be passive, and they will forget these words as they go up to another class.

2.4. Strategies for Teaching Poetry in the Classroom

Sithamparam (2001) concludes that poetry can be approached through three phases: the warming up while listening or reading a poem and the follow-up phase. When incorporating poetry in the classroom teachers should take into consideration the following instructions. First, teachers should provide learners a wide chance to take part in the learning process, such as using pair or group work these ways permit students to express and share their point of view and enhances their interactions. Second, teachers should prepare tasks that are reachable, applicable, and should not be beyond their level of proficiency, besides they should be motivating. Finally, teachers should keep in their minds that the purpose of these strategies is to help the learners to use the language effectively and improve their language skills.

The warming up stage purpose is the prepare learners for the poem. Duff and Maley (1989) propose several ways to prepare students mentally for targeted poetry like using images, recording students' reactions, performing drama, or role-playing and writing. Sithamparam (2001) suggests that teachers can prepare a group of questions to attract their attention to the presented poetry. Further, he recommends that questions should be challenging. Sithamparam (2001) thinks that the first reading is very vital for the students if it accomplishes it appropriately. Therefore, he recommends that teachers should perform the first reading, as teachers' reading make it more memorable and understandable for learners, also he insists that teachers should practice reading before conducting the lessons. When students listen to their teachers reading the poem, they develop an understanding to what they listen to. Learners' reciting is a very beneficial way to get personal responses and reinforce the appreciation of poetry.

Also, reading poetry aloud allows the students to practice its features like pitch, rhyme, and rhythm and enhance their speaking. The final stage is the follow-up. The purpose of this stage is to make sure the learners understand the poem. This can be done by relating the theme of poetry to students' lives or experiences. Also, teachers can ask students to gather their favorite poems and pick them up to memorize by heart to re-enjoy their pleasure without a need to go back to a poetry book or a teacher.

Besides, learners can perform poetry through mime or role-playing. Moreover, teachers can increase real interaction by providing different writing activities and allow students to express their thoughts and feelings. For example, teachers can ask students to rewrite the poem from different perspectives, or make a comic strip, use the title of the poem to write an essay, or even ask them to write their poems using their language.

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

The research design used in this research is qualitative research. Qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning of individuals or group ascribe to a social or human problem.

3.2. Participants

The population in this research was all students of the English Department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate, and the samples of this research were 20 fifth-semester students of the English department of STKIP Kie Raha Ternate.

3.3. Techniques of Data Collection and Data Analysis

To collect the data the researcher used classroom observation and documentation. Classroom observation in this research means that the researcher did monitor or observed the students when they do classroom presentations about English poems. While documentation means in this research like document used in the teaching and learning process.

To analyze the data, the researcher was analyzed the data from the result of classroom observation or in other words the researcher analyzes the result of classroom presentation. When the students present the classroom presentation it is about English poems and how the students analyzed English poems that they presented by using descriptive techniques. The data were gotten in the form of grade (range 0-100) and the grading quality (bad (0-20), low (21-40), fair (41-60), good (61-80), and excellent (81-100)).

4. Finding and Discussion

The data of the result gotten are related to the students' ability in understanding poetry. Then, the data themselves described the students' ability in understanding English poetry through classroom presentation by considering following indicators such as basic of versification it is about accent or unaccented of a poem, Stanzaic forms, poetic feet, metrical lines, blank and free verse of a poem, end-stopped line and run on the line and figurative of language.

Table 1: Students' Scores

No	Ss	Scores
1	BS	80
2	DLN	70
3	HB	55
4	AS	73
5	PT	80
6	RR	77
7	AA	75
8	YS	80
9	HMS	85
10	NA	77
11	ER	70
12	LU	79
13	MK	80
14	RC	83
15	WI	75
16	FM	75
17	IU	65
18	EL	80
19	SD	79

20	ND	56
TOTAL		1494

Based on the table above, the researcher can describe that 2 students got the result are excellent with the score 85 and 83. Because when they did the presentation of the poem and the analysis of the poem are very good. When they read the poem, they have good pronunciation and based on the accent or unaccented of their poem analysis only two or three words in a line of their poem that they forgot to how to pronoun the words. While the other basic versification like Stanzaic forms, poetic feet, metrical lines, blank and free verse of a poem, end-stopped line and run on the line, and figurative of the language they made correctly.

16 students got good result. 5 students got to score 80, 2 students got to score 79, 2 students got to score 77, 3 students got to score 75, 1 student got to score 73, 2 students got to score 70, and 1 student got to score 65. While there are 2 students got the result are fair. 1 student got a score of 56 and 1 student got a score of 55. The two students are still confused about how to read a good poem with a good pronunciation based on the accent or unaccented of their poem analysis, besides that they also still confused about poetic feet. And there was not a student who got a low and bad score.

Poetry is one of the literary works which has to be mastered by the students. It becomes necessary because it provides many benefits to the students. Thus, they have to own understanding of poetry and the basic versification of poetry. Based on the finding, most of the students got a good criterion in understanding poetry. There are only two students who got a fair criterion. While, by having a good comprehension of poetry, the students can take many good impacts on the students themselves. According to Sage (1987) having competency in poetry influences the special quality of life because it gives emotional benefits and cultural transmitter. Thus, good in poetry provides an important contribution to personal capacity and language learning.

The sound of a poem is a way to make poetry more attractive. In this case, the students were demanded to have the competency to understand the repetition of a sound in the poetry and the forms of patterns of stresses in a line or verse. While, based on the finding, there is most students get good criteria in understanding sound. Meanwhile, a few of the students get a low criterion in the understanding sound of poetry. It means that the students have understood the sound of poetry. The sound of poetry is important to comprehend by the students. According to Vardell and Hadaway (2011) comprehending the sound of poetry, rhyme, and rhythm, is an optimal way to learning the language for the learner. In addition, according to Çubukçu (2001) in Rai (2012) having good experience in rhyming and rhythm of the poetry, will give a good contribution to language learning. The students become more familiar with English as the target language. Ara (2009) adds the mastering sound of poetry accommodates the students to convert the meaning of the poetry. Hence, by understanding the sound of poetry, it helps the students improve their competency in English.

Furthermore, based on the result, no student is getting low and bad criteria in understanding the sense of poetry. Most of the students get a satisfactory criterion in the understanding of poetry. It means that a few of the students do not understand the sense of poetry. They faced difficulties to conceive the sense of poetry that connects feeling and emotion. While the competency owned by the students in the sense of poetry contributes to the students themselves in learning a language. According to Norris

(2010) learning poetry offers many benefits to the students consist of some contents. One of them is a sense of poetry itself.

Based on the result of Teaching English poetry in EFL classrooms through classroom presentation there are many benefits of introducing English poetry into an EFL classroom. Poetry introduces the students to a part of the culture of the language they are studying, a part that they may have few opportunities, if any, to experience in the target language. It also gives them a higher forum in which to use and practice the language skills they are learning. The researcher says a higher forum because poetry is often considered to be an elevated, as well as elusive, form of communication. Many students say they cannot understand English poetry and how to analyze it. However, this does not mean we should not attempt to help them understand poetry. The very least English Language students can get from studying poetry is some new vocabulary, some practice inferring meaning from context, and some exposure to a piece of art from the target language. The most that a student can gain is immeasurable, for it can range from a sense of achievement to inspiration.

Teaching English poetry as a model in an EFL curriculum to reinforce students' grammatical and lexical knowledge, and promote their creative writing skills. An insightful statement on studying literature by Hill (1986:7) reads, "The study of literature begins in delight and ends in wisdom". One very effective way to combine these two 105 essential elements of educational and entertainment value is through the use of poems. Using poem in lower-intermediate or intermediate level second language classroom as a model is beneficial for not only the variety and innovation it adds to traditional course bound EFL teaching but also the improvement of learners' grammatical and lexical knowledge provided the objectives for its inclusion and the selection criteria are well established.

5. Conclusion

Based on the description of the result above the researcher can conclude that teaching English poetry in EFL Class through classroom presentation has improved or increased students' comprehension of poems and enhanced the participation of the fifth-semester students of the English Department at STKIP Kie Raha Ternate. Through classroom presentation, the students could read the English poem and analyze the poem based on the basics of the versification of the poem and present it in front of the class. Classroom presentation has given theoretical and practical ways in comprehending poems step by step, asking and answering the questions, sharing opinions, helping each other, giving feedback to complete the teacher's tasks, and analyze the basic versification of the poem. Teaching poetry in the EFL classroom sometimes is hard for the teachers. One of the challenges is the choice of poetry which suits each student but if the teacher can explain more and give more understanding about poetry subject, it is attractive to the students in the teaching and learning process.

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